

LINGUOCOGNITIVE SIGNIFICANCE OF GAMES

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ABSTRACT

The mental development and growth of the child is a continuous process. During this period, there is the development of his formation as a person, his desire, interest and feelings to realize the universe for the first time through the objects around him and find a special meaning in it. In the formation of a child as a harmonious generation, it is necessary to take into account their linguocognitive abilities.

In today's era of globalization, the development of the educational system, the Giving of knowledge, talents and skills in accordance with the world templates to the growing younger generation, the development of their intellectual abilities, has risen to the level of Public Policy. Work on the reform of preschool education in our republic is aimed at further improving this area. The employees of these institutions are assigned such colossal tasks as the development of the child as both spiritual and physically healthy, constant control over each of his conditions. At the same time, preschool education aims to shape child chess as healthy and mature, prepared for school. This covers the period of our sons and daughters from 2 to 6-7 years.

In order to educate the younger generation physically and spiritually competently, consistent work is being carried out in these institutions to teach foreign languages to the little ones, to organize sports and artistic circles. At present, English, German, French languages, rhythmic gymnastics, Chess, Checkers, speech training and other clubs are functioning in preschool institutions in our country. In order to teach children the rich history of our people, national traditions and values, a spirituality room, museums, libraries have been established in preschool educational institutions.

The pedagogical process aimed at ensuring the comprehensive development of preschool children is complex and diverse. The timely implementation of educational work depends on the correct Organization of the pedagogical process in preschool educational institutions, each type of activity.

Educator-educators determine the content and function of training, choose methods and techniques, direct and organize the cognitive activity of children, mastering knowledge, skills and abilities. (A.P.Usova).

When using interactive methods in the process of training, the following rules should be given:

1. Taking into account the age characteristics of children and their attitude towards each other;
2. Using materials of interest to children during the training process;
3. Looking for styles that attract attention and attention;
4. Wide application in gaming processes;

The role, role of Game technologies in educational activities, as well as the mutual harmony of game elements and education are largely determined by how much the teacher understands the essence, function and types of pedagogical games.

Game structure G as a process. Selevko's interpretation covers the following:

- roles taken to play;
- these are game actions that are a means of playing roles;
- replacing real things with conditional ones;
- real interaction of participants in the game;
- content of conditionally created plots in the game.

Practical games used in educational practice are inherently didactic in nature, thus being referred to in many cases as "didactic games".

Even in all periods of its historical development, the game is recognized as the first and most important type of activity of the subject. Consequently, important types of personality activity – Labor, study, as well as play-are important in its formation and development. The basis of life experience, acquired knowledge, lifestyle and social attitudes accumulated by the older generation through games, cultural values were consistently transmitted to the younger generation.

The game has the characteristics of nurturing, developing, provoking an individual. Due to its existing characteristics, games have long been one of the important foundations of folk pedagogy. Indirect games serve to educate children in the field of perception, intuition, memory, thinking, speech by helping them develop mahnavik-morally, mentally, physically and aesthetically. A preschool child is prepared for study and work in play activities.

The game is considered an important type of personality activity and a form of assimilation of the content of social relations on the basis of imitation (displacement, imitation) by children

Games that allow practical games to simulate the organization of certain practical actions are somewhat reduced. The educational significance of games is preserved throughout the life of the child.

If games that serve to promote physical behavior educate agility, agility, endurance, solitude in children, intellectual, constructional games teach them to think, think, reflect logically.

"The game is the leading type of activity that determines the spiritual development of a person for each period of his life. Only in the game and through the game does the child learn about reality, including the social relationships, the hulks, behavior of people".

In situations where the game is aimed at mastering and recreating social experiences, it is defined as the type of activity and in the process of play, the control of the individual's own behavior is formed and improved.

Of particular importance in the composition of the personality of children is the moral pattern of adults. But in the formation of high qualities, human qualities, it is therefore not enough, because if a child does not actively act on himself, does not participate in collaborative activities, then no mahaal behavioral skills will be formed-we want to focus the main attention below on action games.

Action play is a type of activity carried out through a certain physical behavior, in which mainly children carry out behavior based on the following system. Need-goal - plan-action-conclusion-New need.

On the basis of the above system, the child forms his activities and directs. It is from this system that the pre-preparation of the child for action game activities is manifested in the process of the educator explaining the game, it is manifested that he must reflect the entire type of activity in the brain in a holistic way, and then perform his actions, and after performing it, analyze and synthesize his activities.

This can be seen from the systems cited above, as far as mental actions lie on the basis of each action game as well. For this reason, the impact of action games on the mental maturation of the child is incomparable, so to speak, there is no mistake.

In the science of the psychology of age periods, it is known that action games are divided into several types. Action games: done individually, in a team manner.

The fact that all of the above types of games directly and indirectly affect the formation of mental maturation of a child has been proven by many world-famous psychologists.

To an individual action game: ball-playing, rope-jumping, beckoning, chilling, etc. In these action games, the child acts alone for his victory and discusses the outcome of his action alone.

The child reflects his behavior generalizing so that he can analyze-synthesize the outcome of the game, and tries to increase accuracy in his behavior by directing his conscious activity to subsequent games. And as a result, the mental activity of consciousness is improved. At the same time, his skills in relation to the gameplay increase and discover new-new types of action. Therefore itself is an example of the mental formation of children in play activities.

The person directing the child's behavior needs to understand that his physical strength, not dexterity, but, on the contrary, mental orientation is the main factor. Only then can Action Play affect the mental development of the child. Otherwise, the activity of this game will become the sum of actions, consisting only of errors and repetitions. This negatively affects the mental development of the child. The fact that individual action play affects children in most cases in two ways is demonstrated by the doctor of psychological sciences, professor E.G'.Goziev has described: "While individual games always generate negative states such as winning," boredom, manliness"for a child, disdain for others, constantly losing can have consequences such as insecurity, self-deprecation, and alienation". So that a certain amount of individual action game is determined, the reason for its conditionality is, as can be seen by itself, to ensure that a state of "boredom" does not occur during the gameplay. Observing individual game activities, in children, we are teaching each child to analyze his actions, while we are able to influence his mental development.

The second main type of action game is team play, in which each child is responsible for the behavior of others while acting for the majority. This behavior can directly cause a good reflection, generalizing the essence of the action being done for the team. It is natural that the

state of enjoying or being affected by the behavior of the team is reflected in each team member in relation to the general community.

We can example team games – “white terracotta-blue Poplar” from National Games, “cat and mouse”, “rat circular”, “Dorboz”, “guest-guest” games and various competitive games such as volleyball, football, carousel.

Plot role-playing games, meaningful games should also stand out.

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